

DETECTION OF ANOMALIES IN IMAGES BY MACHINE LEARNING FAST RANDOM FOREST –FRF- ALGORITHM

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The Fast Random Forest (FRF) algorithm [*] is able to classify anomalies in an image. The learning process of the algorithm is based on a preliminary classification of cluster of pixels embedding the shape of the anomaly to detect in the whole image. An output of the FRF algorithm is the probabilistic map indicating the high probability to identify an anomaly in a specified image region.

Figure: example of application of FRF algorithm detecting a shape representing an anomaly: original image containing the anomaly to detect (above), and probabilistic map enhancing the defect (below).

Reference

[*] A. Massaro, "Electronic in Advanced Research Industry: From Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0 Advances" Wiley/IEEE , November 2021, ISBN: 9781119716877.